

This is the author's accepted manuscript of a work that was published in 12th International Conference on Advances in Electronic and Photonic Technologies (ADEPT), 2024. The final version is available at proceedings of ADEPT

DESIGN OF PACKAGING OF POWER DMOS TRANSISTOR

P. Príbytný*, A. Chvála, J. Marek

Institute of Electronics and Photonics, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava,
Ilkovičova 3, 812 19 Bratislava, Slovakia
e-mail: patrik.pribytny@stuba.sk

Abstract *Simulation study of packaging of a power DMOS transistor is presented. The analysis is focused on the optimization of the design in order to improve electrical properties of the device. The simulation results shows that optimized design can improve the switching speed of the power DMOS transistor. The lower parasites inductance and resistance of the ribbon-bond source electrode improves the switching speed of the power DMOS transistor about 13 %.*

Keywords packaging, Power DMOS Transistor, switching speed

1. INTRODUCTION

Power DMOS transistors are irreplaceable for power electronics and circuits. Indeed, the silicon-based DMOS are widely accepted as the power device of choice for medium and high-power applications [1, 2]. During the constant development of the devices in order to increase the switching speed, power losses reduction, and thermal management improvement, there is a required optimization of the power DMOS devices. Simulation and modeling represent powerful tools for the analysis, characterization, and optimization of the devices. Simulation can define critical areas in the device and significantly shorten the time and cost of the device manufacturing during the development and optimization stage [3].

In this paper, we present the optimization of electrical properties of power DMOS supported by 3-D device simulation in COMSOL Multiphysics [4]. Two die bonding methods of DMOS, wire-bond and ribbon-bond, are analyzed and compared. Simulation results demonstrated that the optimized ribbon-bond concept has better electrical and switching performance than the wire-bond.

2. STRUCTURE AND SIMULATION DESCRIPTION

The device under investigation is power DMOS transistor. The transistor is packaged in a PowerFLAT5x6 package. 3-D electro-magnetic finite element method (FEM) simulations of the device are performed in COMSOL Multiphysics. Parasitic inductances and resistances of drain, gate, and source electrodes are solved by Magnetic Fields, Current Only module. Finally the parasitic properties of the electrodes are added to the circuit model of the power DMOS transistor. Switching speed is evaluated in LTspice circuit simulator.

3. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three die bonding methods are analyzed and compared (Fig. 2). The first and second methods use one wire and multi wires for bonding of semiconductor chip in the package. It is a widely used method for its low cost and high reliability [5]. However, the wire-bond method exhibits high parasitic resistance and inductance. The second method is based on the ribbon-bond concept. The ribbon-bond concept can handle high current and low resistance.

Fig. 1 One wire-bond, three wires-bond and ribbon-bond power DMOS.

Table 1 Comparison of the parasitic inductance and resistance of three die bonding methods of power DMOS transistor.

	1 wire	3 wires	Ribbon
L_{SOURCE}	1.99 μH	1.49 μH	1.22 μH
L_{DRAIN}	0.135 μH		
L_{GATE}	2.76 μH		
R_{SOURCE}	8.48 $\text{m}\Omega$	3.3 $\text{m}\Omega$	1.55 $\text{m}\Omega$
R_{DRAIN}	0.25 $\text{m}\Omega$		
R_{GATE}	18.2 $\text{m}\Omega$		

This is the author's accepted manuscript of a work that was published in 12th International Conference on Advances in Electronic and Photonic Technologies (ADEPT), 2024. The final version is available at proceedings of ADEPT

Table 1 shows the comparison of electro-magnetic properties of the drain, gate, and source electrodes for three die bonding methods. The parasitic inductance L and resistance R of drain, gate, and source interconnections were analyzed. The highest source parasitic inductance and resistance has one wire-bond. The ribbon-bond has lowest values of the parasitic inductance and resistance.

After 3-D electro-magnetic FEM simulation and evaluation of the parasitic properties of electrodes, circuit simulation of switching of power DMOS transistor were performed. Time of turn on and turn off the drain current I_D was analyzed.

Fig. 2 Transistor switching time response for one wire-bond, three wire-bonds, and ribbon-bond lead to the source electrode.

This is the author's accepted manuscript of a work that was published in 12th International Conference on Advances in Electronic and Photonic Technologies (ADEPT), 2024. The final version is available at proceedings of ADEPT

A smaller value of inductance mainly affects the delay of switching of the transistor. Fig. 2 shows the time response of drain current I_D on switching of input gate voltage V_{GS} for the analyzed power DMOS transistor with different die bonding methods. The one wire-bond structure has the largest delay (~23 ns) and the ribbon-bond structure has the smallest (~20 ns).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Optimization of electrical properties of power DMOS transistor supported by 3-D electro-magnetic simulation was presented. Simulation results demonstrated that the optimized ribbon-bond concept has better electrical performance than wire-bonding of power DMOS transistor. The lower parasites inductance and resistance of the ribbon-bond source electrode improves the switching speed of the power DMOS transistor about 13 %.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the project FastLane. The project is supported by the Chips Joint Undertaking (JU) and its members, including top-up funding by Austria, France, Germany, Romania, and Slovakia under grant agreement No 101139788. This work was also supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under contract No. APVV-20-0266 and by grant VEGA 1/0543/23 supported by the Ministry of Education, Research, Development and Youth of the Slovak Republic.

References

- [1] Vogt, F. et al., *Proc. 9th Int. Symp. Power Semiconductor Devices and IC's*, Weimar, Germany (1997).
- [2] Williams, R. K. et al. *IEEE Tran. on Electron Devices*, 64, 3, 692-712 (2017).
- [3] Chvala, A. et al., *IEEE Trans. on Electron Devices*, 64, 1, 333-336 (2017).
- [4] COMSOL Multiphysics® v. 6.2 www.comsol.com.
- [5] Jang, H.G, et al., *Int. Conf. on Electronics, Information, and Communication ICEIC* (2021).